

Orthohydroxyketones and Orthohydroxyketoximes as Indicators for the Direct CyDTA Titration of Ferric Ions

M. N. DESAI, K. C. DESAI, B. S. PATWARI AND
M. H. GANDHI

Chemistry Department, University School of Sciences,
Gujarat University, Ahmedabad-9

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MARPLE¹ showed the superior accuracy of cyDTA compared to the direct EDTA titration of iron. According to him the end point with chrome Azurol S is much more easily determined than that with thiocyanate or sulphosalicylic acid. It is to be noted however that miligram-amounts of aluminium react with chrome Azurol S to give a violet colour

The optimum pH is 1.0–2.0. 2 drops of 1% indicator solution give satisfactory results. The titrations can be carried out in the temperature range 15°–50°C.

Effect of foreign ions: The titration of synthetic solutions were carried out at pH 1.0. At 1.4 mg concentration of iron, 100 times excess of Na⁺, K⁺, NH₄⁺, Cl⁻, Br⁻, ClO₄⁻, NO₃⁻, SO₄²⁻, 50 times excess of UO₂²⁺, 20 times excess of Mg²⁺, Ca²⁺, Sr²⁺, Ba²⁺, Ni²⁺, Co²⁺, 10 times excess of Ag⁺, Pb²⁺, Al³⁺, 5 times excess of Zn²⁺, Cd²⁺, and an equal amount of Cu²⁺ could be tolerated. Mn²⁺, Th⁴⁺, Zr⁴⁺ anions forming stable complex with iron such as phosphates, vanadates, molybdates and tungstates interfered at all levels.

Synthetic solutions containing more than one foreign ions were also analysed with the help of these indicators at pH 1.0. Results are shown in Table 1.

TABLE 1. ANALYSIS OF SYNTHETIC SOLUTIONS

Metals present	Found Fe ³⁺ mg			
	Orthohydroxy acetophenone	Orthohydroxy propiophenone	Orthohydroxy acetophenone oxime	Orthohydroxy propiophenone oxime
1. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +1.50 mg Na ⁺ +10 mg Ag ⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80
2. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +25 mg Pd ²⁺ +50 mg K ⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80
3. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Ca ²⁺ +20 mg Sr ²⁺	2.80	2.79	2.80	2.80
4. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Sr ²⁺ +20 mg Ba ²⁺	2.81	2.80	2.80	2.81
5. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +20 mg Fe ²⁺ +20 mg Al ³⁺	2.79	2.80	2.81	2.80
6. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +1 mg Cu ²⁺ +10 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80	2.79	2.80
7. 2.8 mg Fe ³⁺ +10 mg Co ²⁺ +10 mg Ni ²⁺	2.80	2.80	2.80	2.80

which obscures the endpoint for the iron titration. The conditions for the use of thiocyanate indicator are very restrictive. According to Martinez² with sulphosalicylic acid and iron results are high upto 4%. The present paper reports the use of *o*-hydroxy acetophenone, orthohydroxy propiophenone, *o*-hydroxy acetophenone oxime and orthohydroxy-propiophenone oxime as indicators for the direct titration of iron using CyDTA.

Experimental

CyDTA solution: A stock solution of 0.01M CyDTA was prepared by dissolving 3.4 g of CyDTA and 1.6 g sodium hydroxide in 1 lt of distilled water.

Observations: Orthohydroxy acetophenone, orthohydroxy propiophenone, orthohydroxybutyrophenone, orthohydroxyacetophenone oxime, orthohydroxypropiofenone oxime and orthohydroxybutyrophenone oxime give violet colours with ferric ions. Preliminary studies indicated that orthohydroxy butyrophenone and its oxime are not satisfactory indicators; hence the remaining compounds were investigated in detail.

The end point is marked by a sharp colour change from purple to deep yellow on titration with CyDTA.

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References

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Gravimetric and Volumetric Determination of Cd, Zn and Pd as Isoquinoline Halide Complexes and the Simultaneous Determination of Cd-Cu, Cd-Co, Cd-Ni, Zn-Ni, Zn-Cu and Zn-Co

A. L. J. RAO AND B. K. PURI

Department of Chemistry, Punjabi University, Patiala

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CADMIUM and zinc were detected as pyridine bromide and pyridine iodide complexes¹. Though this reaction is quite specific for these metals, yet no attempt has been made so far for their determination based upon these reactions. These metals